

Title: Cosmology with the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope

Thematic areas: Cosmology, Dark Energy, Astronomy & Astrophysics

Primary author: Rogerio Rosenfeld

Contact person: Rogerio Rosenfeld (rogerio.rosenfeld@unesp.br)

Webpage of the project: <https://www.lsst.org/>

Abstract:

The LSST will perform a 10-year photometric survey of the sky using a new telescope with an effective 8.4 meter mirror and the largest digital camera ever constructed with 3.2 gigapixels a 3.5 degree field of view and weighing 2.8 tons. Among other goals, the LSST will explore the nature of Dark Matter and Dark Energy that comprises 95% of the energy budget of the Universe today. It will do so by analyzing the enormous amount of data that will be collected (~20 terabytes/night) about the distribution of galaxies, the number of cluster of galaxies, of supernovae and the distortions of the shape of galaxies produced by intervening matter.

Proposal Overview

- Scientific context

The nature of dark energy and dark matter is not known. In spite of its great successes in explaining all the cosmological observations so far, the so-called Λ CDM model is not satisfactory since the origin of the cosmological constant (Λ) and the nature of the cold dark matter (CDM) is left undetermined. Several experiments, such as the Planck satellite, the South Pole Telescope, BICEPS, DES, DESI, Euclid, among others have been designed to explore these issues. In fact, there are already some signs of tension in the Λ CDM model that will be scrutinized in the near future and may indicate the need for New Physics.

Among the experiments under construction, the LSST will obtain the largest amount of data after its 10-year operation. In a sense the LSST is a continuation of the Dark Energy Survey project, using the same photometric techniques with a much larger data sample.

- Objectives

Study the nature of dark energy and dark matter using LSST data. In addition, the data will also be used to address a host of other astrophysical topics not necessarily related to cosmology.

- Methodology

Use measurements of the galaxy distribution, weak lensing, supernova and cluster counts to find the best parameters that describe the data in a given theoretical model using a bayesian framework.

- List of interested scientists

The brazilian participation in the LSST is coordinated by the Laboratório Interinstitucional de e-Astronomia (LineA – linea.gov.br) and more details can be found in <http://www.linea.gov.br/010-ciencia/1-projetos/4-lsst/>

At this moment there are 9 Principal Investigators (PI) from different institutions in Brazil working in LSST through a Memorandum of Agreement:

1. Julio Bueno de Camargo, Observatório Nacional / MCTIC
2. Luiz Nicolaci da Costa, Observatório Nacional, LineA
3. Marcos Vinicius B. Lima, Uiversidade de São Paulo
4. Valerio Marra, Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo
5. Ricardo Ogando, Observatório Nacional, LineA

6. Rogerio Rosenfeld, Instituto de Física Teórica -UNESP
7. Basílio Santiago, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul
8. Flávia Sobreira, Universidade Estadual de Campinas
9. Mariana Penna Vitenti, Universidade de Brasília

In addition, each PI can appoint up to 4 junior members (students and posdocs) and at the moment there are 19 such members registered in LSST:

1. Banda-Huarca, Martín Valentín, Observatório Nacional / MCTIC
2. Benedetti-Rossi, Gustavo, Observatório Nacional / MCTIC
3. Bouffleur, Rodrigo, Observatório Nacional / MCTIC
4. Rommel, Flavia, Observatório Nacional / MCTIC
5. Gomes, Daniel Charles Heringer, Universidade de São Paulo
6. Gomes, Rafael Charles Heringer, Universidade de São Paulo
7. Baqui, Pedro Otavio Souza, Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo
8. Ferreira, Tassia Andrade, Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo
9. Silva, Rodrigo Duarte, Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo
10. Agüena, Michel, IF/USP, LIneA
11. dos Santos, Hillysson, Observatório Nacional, LIneA
12. Gschwend, Julia, Observatório Nacional, LIneA
13. Ferreira, Nelson, Instituto de Física Teórica -UNESP
14. Troja, Antonino, Instituto de Física Teórica -UNESP
15. Dal Ponte, Marina, Observatório Nacional, LIneA
16. Pieres, Adriano, Observatório Nacional, LIneA
17. Brandão de Souza, Anderson Luiz, Universidade Estadual de Campinas
18. Camacho, Hugo, IFT-UNESP and LIneA
19. Vitenti, Sandro Dias Pinto, Universidade de Brasília

The list of participants can also be found in:

<https://www.lsstcorporation.org/sites/default/files/Named%20PIs-JRs%202019-11-04.pdf>

Some members will work on topics not directly related to Cosmology.

- Current status, timeline and expected challenges

The LSST is scheduled to start a Science Verification run in 2021 and observations should start in 2022, lasting until 2032.

The biggest challenge will be the analysis of the huge amount of data generated by the LSST. Massive computational resources are necessary for photometric redshift estimation of a billion galaxies, production of galaxy catalogs, weak lensing catalogs, cluster catalogs, supernova catalogs and for running the analysis pipelines.

- Construction and operational costs

Money for the construction and operational costs for the LSST has already been secured. The participation of 10 PI's from Brazil will not cost any additional money since it was paid by in-kind contribution.

- Current computing infrastructure and future requirements

LIneA's computer facilities is presently dedicated to DES and LSST work and consist of three clusters (SGI ALTIX, SGI ICE-X and HPE Apollo 2000) yielding a combined total of approximately 25 Tflops of computing power that will operate at 100Gb/s as soon as the new storage acquired is installed. Besides, all LIneA's computing infrastructure is hosted at a supercomputing facility at a partner institute - the Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica (LNCC). It also allows us to have easy access to a supercomputer called Santos Dumont which has 1 PFLOPS available for shared use (its use relies on a project submission and approval). It is expected that by 2021 our dedicated computing power will increase to over 100 Tflops with funds already allocated to LIneA by the federal funding agency FINEP. Both systems could be used to implement the proposed computations. Regarding storage environment, there is over 600 TB available for short/long-term data retention and for backup purposes. In addition, we recently acquired a tiered Lustre storage solution in order to support the HPC workloads, which has read/write performance of 12 GB/s and 570 TB of initial space. In terms of scalability, the solution itself can be scaled up to 5 PB of total space or "unlimited" space (as the budget allows) if needed, due to the tiered approach adopted.

We also intend to propose to the LSST the implementation of an iDAC (independent Data Access Center) in Brazil. This will likely be done in collaboration with the LNCC and RNP (Brazilian NREN) which are planning to jointly create a Center to support e-Science. Its cost is estimated at U\$10 million in 10 years. LIneA's role would be to provide technical and scientific assistance and be the interface to LSST. We plan to use the experience LIneA has accumulated maintaining a mirror site of SDSS and developing interfaces to explore the DES database. Network throughputs of 10 Gbps are already available to LNCC and is expected to be upgraded to 100 Gbps before the start of LSST operations. By having the iDAC in Brazil will facilitate the contributions mentioned above with the data near the available computing infrastructure.